

THE STRUCTURE OF THE FORMATION OF NOUNS WITH THE SUFFIX “-NESS” AND THE USE OF NOUNS WITH THE SUFFIX “-NESS” IN LITERARY WORKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320535>

Abstract: It is obvious that suffixes play an essential role in the formation of new words as they can help to create new meaningful unit with adding various kinds of suffixes to the stem or the root of the word. In this article, our focus is on the formation of the nouns with the help of the suffix “-ness”. We try to analyze how they are formed, what changes may occur and what kind of parts of speech the suffix “-ness” can transform to the nouns. In addition, we give examples for the nouns with the suffix “-ness” from the literary works.

Keywords: suffixation, derivational, parts of speech, stem, lexical, meaning, formation, lexicology, noun, verb, adverb, adjective, noun suffix, state, condition, quality.

The English language contains an enormous and ever-growing number of words. The process of enhancing our vocabulary can seem overwhelming, but if we know the common prefixes and suffixes of English, we will understand many more words.

Mastering particular prefixes and suffixes is like learning a code that once we crack the code, we cannot only spell words more correctly but also recognize and perhaps even define unfamiliar words.

Prefixes

A prefix is a word part added to the beginning of a word to create a new meaning .

Table 1. Common Prefixes¹

Prefix	Meaning	Example
dis	not, opposite of	Dis + satisfied = dissatisfied
mis	wrongly	Mis + spell = misspell
un	not	Un + acceptable= unacceptable
re	again	Re + election= reelection
inter	between	Inter + related= interrelated
pre	before	Pre + pay= prepay
non	not	Non + sense = nonsense

Suffixes

A suffix is a word part added to the end of a word to create a new meaning. Many words in English are formed from the same root or base word. By adding different suffixes, a range of new words can be formed. In this article, we pay attention to noun suffixes. By the way, we have to claim that when the suffix is added to a base word and that base word becomes a noun, it is called **a noun suffix**. The following suffixes are commonly used noun suffixes:

Table 2. Common Suffixes²

Suffix	Meaning	Example
-ship	(quality or state)	<i>friendship, leadership, membership</i>
-ity	(quality or state)	<i>ability, security, similarity, curiosity</i>
-ness	(quality or state)	<i>happiness, kindness, goodness, laziness</i>
-ment	(forming abstract nouns)	<i>enjoyment, government, management</i>
-sion; -tion	(quality or state)	<i>discussion, population, excursion, question</i>
-ism	(belief, behavior, theory or act of)	<i>humanism, vegetarianism, journalism, egoism</i>
-age	(action, result of)	<i>Breakage, wastage, package</i>

When we add **-ness** to an adjective, it becomes a noun. The suffix **-ness** means “*state, condition and quality*”_and is used with an adjective to say something about the state, condition or quality of being that adjective.

For example, **redness** is a red quality, and **redness** means “the quality of being red”.

- The redness in his eyes went away after he got some sleep.

Bitterness is a bitter condition, or “the condition of being bitter”.

- The breakup caused them to feel anger and bitterness.
- **Sleepyness** means “the condition of being sleepy”.

Not all adjectives can be made into nouns using “-ness”. Typically, if an adjective is in its comparative (-er) or superlative (-est) degrees, “-ness” cannot be added:

- **Higher and highest** cannot become **higherness or highestness**.

Typically, if an adjective is actually a participle of a verb, “-ness” cannot be added:

- **Washed and running** cannot become **washedness or runningness**.

Moreover, suffixes can be derivational and inflectional, but, on the other hand, we have to focus on only derivational suffixes which can change the meaning of the words and also make them a different part of speech.³ For instance, when the suffix **-ness** is added to an adjective, it transforms its meaning as well as its own type and makes it a noun:

² www.Britannica.com – “Suffix Definition & Meaning”, Britannica Dictionary, 2020
³ Lives Trevian “English Suffixes” Peter Lang, monographs, volume 202

- *Bright (adjective) + -ness = brightness (noun)*
- *Close (adjective) + -ness = closeness (noun)*
- *Aware (adjective) + -ness = awareness (noun)*
- *Kind (adjective) + -ness = kindness (noun)*
- *Competitive (adjective) + -ness = competitiveness (noun)*
- *Tender (adjective) + -ness = tenderness (noun)*
- *Assertive (adjective) + -ness = assertiveness (noun)*
- *Responsive (adjective) + -ness = responsiveness (noun)*
- *Frank (adjective) + -ness = frankness (noun)*

In most cases, we often assume that new formed nouns by suffix -ness are made up of words belonging to adjectives. Because there are enough examples for this opinion:

smooth	smoothness
reckless	recklessness
firm	firmness
white	whiteness
permissive	permissiveness
awkward	awkwardness
uneasy	uneasiness
foolish	foolishness
pretentious	pretentiousness
sticky	stickiness
stubborn	stubbornness
homesick	homesickness
casual	casualness
arbitrary	arbitrariness
creditworthy	creditworthiness
resourceful	resourcefulness
uneven	unevenness
vivid	vividness
coarse	coarseness
vindictive	vindictiveness

As the result, after analyzing a range of dictionaries, lexicographical writings and morphological system of units, we have come to the conclusion that the suffix “-ness” makes new meaningful words from the following parts of speech:

- Verbs
- Nouns
- Pronouns
- Adverbs
- Prepositions

Verb + -ness = noun

Word	Suffix	Result
Forgive (stop feeling angry for an offence, mistake)	-ness	Forgiveness (the action of forgiving or being forgiven)
Govern (conduct the policy, actions, organization or people)	-ness	Governess (a woman employed to teach children in private household)
Idle (spend time doing nothing)	-ness	Idleness (a state of inaction or inactivity)
Supple (bend and move easily and gracefully)	-ness	Suppleness (the quality of bending easily without breaking, or being flexible)
Marked (past participle of mark - make a visible impression)	-ness	Markedness (the state of standing out as nontypical or divergent in comparison to a regular or more common form)
Outspoken (past participle of outspeak - to speak openly)	-ness	Outspokenness (the free expression of one's true feelings and opinions)
Broken (past participle of break - separate into pieces)	-ness	Brokenness (the quality of being broken)
Knowing (participle of know - be aware of through observation, inquiry or information)	-ness	Knowingness (the state of having knowledge of)
Given (past participle of give - freely transfer the possession of smth to smb)	-ness	Givenness (the act of giving or yielding)
Lost (past participle of lose - become unable to find)	-ness	Lostness (the state of being lost)
Assured (past participle of assure - tell smb smth positively)	-ness	Assuredness (great coolness and composure under strain)

Noun + -ness = noun

Word	Suffix	Result
Case (an instance of a particular situation)	-ness	Caseness (the degree to which the accepted standardized diagnostic criteria for a given condition are applicable to a given patient)
Rose (a prickly bush or shrub that typically bears red)	-ness	Rosiness (a rosy quality or state)

Hip (a projection of the pelvis and upper thigh none on each side of the body in human beings)	-ness	Hipness (coolness, trendiness)
Expert (a person who is very knowledgeable)	-ness	Expertness (skillfulness by virtue of possessing special knowledge)
Square (a plane figure with for equal straight sides)	-ness	Squareness (the property of being shaped like a square)
Gay (of a person: homosexual)	-ness	Gayness (homosexuality)
Human (relating to humankind)	-ness	Humanness (the quality of being human)
Deer (a hoofed grazing or browsing animal)	-ness	Deerness (the state or quality of being a deer)
Female (relating to woman)	-ness	Femaleness (the properties characteristic of the female sex)
Male (relating to man)	-ness	Maleness (the properties characteristic of the male sex)

Pronoun + -ness = noun

Word	Suffix	Result
Whole (all of, entire)	-ness	Wholeness (the state of forming a complete harmonious whole; unity)
Nothing (not anything)	-ness	Nothingness (the absence or cessation of life or existence)
Other (further, additional)	-ness	Otherness (the quality or fact of being different)
Vast (of very great extent)	-ness	Vastness (very great extent or size, immensity)
Same (the same thing as smth previously mentioned)	-ness	Sameness (the quality of being the same; identity or similarity)

Number + -ness = noun

Word	Suffix	Result
One	-ness	Oneness (the fact or state of being one in number)
Two	-ness	Twoness (the fact or state of being two; duality)

Adverb + -ness = noun

Word	Suffix	Result
Past (used to indicate the lapse of time)	-ness	Pastness (the quality or state of being past)
Much (to a great extent, great deal)	-ness	Muchness (the quality or state of being great in quantity)
Well (in a good or satisfactory way)	-ness	Wellness (the quality or state of being in good health, especially as an actively pursued goal)
Even (used to emphasize smth surprising or extreme)	-ness	Evenness (the characteristic of being regular, smooth, or homogenous)
Together (with or in proximity to another person)	-ness	Togetherness (the state of being close to another person)
Apart (separated by a specified distance in time or space)	-ness	Apartness (the quality of being apart)
Still (up to and including the present or the time mentioned; even now)	-ness	Stillness (the absence of movement or sound)

Preposition + -ness = noun

Word	Suffix	Result
Like (having the same characteristics or qualities as; similar to)	-ness	Likeness (the fact or quality of being alike, resemblance)

➤ **Examples from literary works**

Example #1. "Gulliver`s Travels" by Jonathan Swift

*"Two days after this adventure, the emperor, having ordered that part of his army which quarters in and about his metropolis, to be in **readiness**, took a fancy of diverting himself in a very singular manner."*

Example #2. "Heart of Darkness" by Joseph Conrad

*"... I assure you that never, never before, did this land, this river, this jungle, the very arch of this blazing sky, appear to me so hopeless and so dark, so impenetrable to human thought, so pitiless to human **weakness**."*

Example #3. "Ode to Autumn" by John Keats

*"Season of mists and mellow **fruitfulness**,
Close bosom-friend of the maturing sun...
To bend with apples the moss`d cottage-trees,
And fill all fruit with **ripeness** to the core;*

*Thee sitting careless on a granary floor,
Thy hair soft-lifted by the winnowing wind...*

Taking everything into consideration, we come to these conclusions:

- It is obvious that the suffix *-ness* is not a new suffix to be being used, it was first recorded before 900; Middle English *-nes(s)* (in placenames), in part continuing Old English *naes*, in part from Old Norse *nes*; akin to nose;
- A native English suffix attached to adjectives and participles, forming abstract nouns denoting quality and state (and often, by extension, something exemplifying a quality or state):
- Origin of *-ness*: Middle English, Old English *-nes, -nis*, cognate with German *-nis*, Gothic *-(n)assus*; suffix originally *- assus*; *-n-* by false division of words with adjective and past participle stems ending in *-n-*;⁴
- *-ness* indicates state, condition, or quality, or an instance of one of these: *greatness, selfishness, meaninglessness, a kindness, obligingness, preparedness*;
- *The suffix -ness can make up nouns of not only adjectives but also verbs, nouns, pronouns, adverbs and even prepositions*;
- *Most of the writers and poets used nouns with the suffix -ness in their works and as the result we can say that -ness has been used from old ages till this time.*

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